

Documentation of SAS Syntax for Splitting and Cleaning Diagnosis and Procedure Codes in the National Patient Register

<p>Title: Data Cleaning Syntax for Processing “hdia”, “diagnos”, and “op” Variables from the Swedish National Patient Register</p>
<p>About this document: This document provides SAS syntax used to process the three variables – “hdia”, “diagnos” and “op” – from the National Patient Register, provided by the Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare (Socialstyrelsen). The syntax performs two main tasks:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It separates concatenated diagnosis and procedure codes into 30 individual variables each. 2. For the diagnosis variables, it identifies and extracts entries that do not represent valid diagnosis codes – specifically, codes suspected to be ATC codes and functional status codes – and moves them into dedicated variables. These codes are then replaced with standardized placeholders (“_atc_” and “_func_”) in the diagnosis variables. <p>This data-cleaning procedure complements the initial preprocessing performed by Socialstyrelsen and is part of the broader data preparation workflow for research conducted within the IMAS project.</p>
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<p>Software: SAS (9.4)</p>
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<p>Contents: This syntax includes procedures for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Separating concatenated codes into separate variables. - Identifying and extracting codes suspected to be ATC codes and functional status codes from diagnosis variables.
<p>Purpose: Separating concatenated procedure (OP) and diagnosis (Diagnos) codes into 30 individual variables each.</p>
<p>Description: OP and Diagnos are character variables containing concatenated codes, separated by blank spaces.</p>
<p>Information source: National Patient Register, provided by Socialstyrelsen.</p>
<p>Input variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>OP</i>: Procedure codes. Maximum 30 procedures - <i>Diagnos</i>: Diagnoses according to ICD. Maximum 30 diagnoses
<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30 variables for procedure codes: <i>op1-op30</i>, each containing one procedure code per variable - 30 variables for diagnosis codes: <i>dia1-dia30</i>, each containing one diagnosis code per variable
<p>Syntax: SAS <pre>*****; * Separate the OP and Diagnos variables into 30 OP/ 30 dia variables; *****;</pre></p>

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* OP is a character variable containing concatenated procedure codes,
separated by blank spaces. These codes are split into 30 individual
variables (op1-op30);
* Diagnos is a character variable containing concatenated diagnosis
codes, also separated by blank spaces. Even these are split into 30
individual variables (dial-dia30);
data new_data1 (compress=yes drop=i op diagnos);
set data;
array arrayOP (30) $ op1-op30;
array arrayDIA (30) $ dial-dia30;
do i = 1 to 30;
arrayOP[i] = scan(op,i,' ');
arrayDIA[i] = scan(diagnos,i,' ');
end;
run;

```

Purpose: Identify and extract entries from the diagnosis variables that do not represent valid diagnosis codes.

Description: Non-valid codes – specifically, codes suspected to be ATC codes and functional status codes – are identified and moved to dedicated variables. These codes are then replaced with standardized placeholders ("_atc_" and "_func_") in the original diagnosis variables.

Information source: National Patient Register, provided by Socialstyrelsen.

Input variables:

- *hdia*: Diagnosis code of main diagnosis
- *dia1-dia30*: Diagnosis codes (each variable contains one diagnosis code)

Output:

- *hdia*: Diagnosis code of main diagnosis (with non-valid codes replaced if applicable)
- *dia1-dia30*: Diagnosis codes (with non-valid codes replaced if applicable)
- *atc* and *func*: Two additional variables to store extracted codes suspected to be ATC and functional status codes

Syntax:

SAS

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*****;
* Handle suspected ATC and functional status codes in diagnosis variables
* --> hdia, dial-dia30;
*****;
/*

```

Procedure

- **Identification:** Detect codes that have the typical format of ATC and functional status codes within the diagnosis variables.
- **Extraction:** Move identified codes to the new variables *atc* and *func*.
- **Replacement:** Replace extracted codes in the original diagnosis variables with standardized placeholders:
 - o "_atc_" for ATC codes
 - o "_func_" for functional status codes

Notes

- Socialstyrelsen has already removed certain ATC codes from inpatient data, marking these instances with "_atc".
- This process performs an additional cleaning step to remove remaining codes suspected to be ATC and functional status codes.
- **Important:** The syntax identifies codes that match the typical format of ATC or functional status codes. However, it does not verify whether these codes actually exist, i.e., whether they are valid, recognized ATC or functional status codes.

- Replacement markers:
 - "_atc" → Code removed by Socialstyrelsen
 - "_atc_" → Code removed during this cleaning process

Additional Information

Functional status codes used in inpatient rehabilitation reflect levels of activity limitation, functional impairment, and participation restriction. More details are available from Socialstyrelsen.
*/

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data new_data2 (compress=yes drop=i);
length atc func $100;
set new_data1;
/* The diagnosis variables are defined as the 31 elements of the array
"diags". */
array diags (31) hdia dial1-dia30;
/* An iteration from 1 to 31 is performed to loop through the array of
diagnosis variables: hdia (position 1) and dial1-dia30 (positions 2-31).*/
do i=1 to 31;
/* Codes matching the format of ATC codes are identified based on the
following pattern:
- Position 1: Must be one of the letters A, B, C, D, G, H, J, L, M, N,
P, R, S, or V
- Position 2: Must be the digit 0 or 1
- Position 3: Must be a digit (0-9)
- Position 4: Must be a letter (A-Z)
- Position 5: Must be a letter (A-Z)
If a diagnosis string matches this pattern, it is classified as a
suspected ATC code. The code is then moved to the variable 'atc'
(multiple codes are space-separated), and replaced with "_atc_" in the
original diagnosis variable.*/
if substr(diags(i),1,1) in
("A","B","C","D","G","H","J","L","M","N","P","R","S","V") and
substr(diags(i),2,1) in ("0", "1") and
anydigit(substr(diags(i),3,1))=1 and
anyalpha(substr(diags(i),4,1))=1 and
anyalpha(substr(diags(i),5,1))=1 then do;
atc = catx(" ", atc, diags(i));
diags(i)="_atc_";
end;
/* Codes matching the format of functional status codes are identified
based on the following pattern:
- Position 1: Must be the letter "U"
- Position 2: Must be one of the letters "A", "B", or "P"
If a diagnosis string matches this pattern, it is classified as a
suspected functional status code. The code is then moved to the variable
'func' (multiple codes are space-separated), and replaced with "_func_"
in the original diagnosis variable.*/
if substr(diags(i),1,1) = "U" and substr(diags(i),2,1) in ("A", "B", "P")
then do;
func = catx(" ", func, diags(i));
diags(i)="_func_";
end;
end;
run;

```

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